

Cyrus-Junior Soccer Simulation 2D Team Description Paper 2024

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Abstract. This Team Description Paper presents an overview of recent works of Cyrus-Junior. Last year we have been trying to use different methods for players' positioning and formation system. One method we found interesting and useful is the "Delaunay triangulation" for creating formation for our players. We are going to present this method in this paper.

Keywords: Soccer Simulation 2D · Delaunay triangulation · Voronoi diagram
IranOpen · RoboCup

1 Introduction

We have been participating in Soccer Simulation 2D leagues since 2022 with the name of EMPEROR. Our first competition was in IranOpen2022 starter league. In IranOpen2023 we participated in both starter and major league. In addition to that, we participated in RoboCup2023. IranOpen 2023 was a very critical competition for us as we achieved to be the champion of Soccer Simulation 2D-starter league. Later that year in RoboCup2023 we got the first place in starter challenge. We have been improving our team with the aim of remaining on the top of the competition table.

Note: We are using StarterAgent2D-V2 as our base in starter league [1]. StarterAgent2D-V2 is a simplified version of Helios-Base (Agent2D) which some parts of it for example ChainAction and Formation have been removed or simplified.

2 Related work

Now, we will mention some articles published by other Soccer simulation 2D teams. HELIOS developed "Player's MatchUp" algorithm for exchanging players' positions during the game for better team performance [2]. CYRUS uses opponent's pass prediction for marking and teammate's pass prediction for unmarking [3]. Persepolis optimized its offensive strategy by randomly placing players in the soccer 2D field and training them for the best attack [4]. MT2022 used HFO (Half Field Offense) for training and testing their shoot algorithm [5]. CYRUS 2023 reduced noise in Soccer Simulation 2D by using different methods including Deep Neural Networks (DNNs) and Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks [6]. HELIOS2023 enhanced ball

chasing behavior by using Learning methods such as Learning-to-rank method [7]. YuShan proposed a method based on kernel density negative example learning, which improved the classification effect of different kinds of passing feature data by parsing the game log files [8].

3 Delaunay triangulation

3.1 Delaunay triangulation in theory

In mathematics and computational geometry, a Delaunay triangulation for given points is a triangulation such that no point is inside the circumcircle of the generated triangles. Circumcenter is the point, where the bisectors of a triangle intersect and has the same distance from all of the triangle's nodes. This type of triangulation limits the number of triangles with small angles.

Fig. 1. A simple Delaunay triangulation is shown in this figure. You can see the number of triangles with small angle is limited using this method.

3.2 Relationship of Delaunay triangulation with the Voronoi diagram

The circumcenters of the Delaunay triangles are the vertices of the Voronoi diagram.

In the 2D case, the Voronoi vertices are connected via edges, that can be derived from adjacency-relationships of the Delaunay triangles: If two triangles share an edge in the Delaunay triangulation, their circumcenters should be connected with an edge in the Voronoi diagram.

Fig. 2. The right figure is Delaunay triangulation and the left figure is the circumcenters of the right figure connected together forming a Voronoi diagram.

3.3 Usage of Delaunay triangulation in players' formation algorithm

One of the most effortless ways to create formation for players is to use fedit2 [8] which is a graphical app implemented for creating and generating formation for Soccer Simulation 2D players.

Fig. 3. Screenshot from fedit2 and arranging players' positions.

After arranging players' positions based on created points and saving the formation file, fedit2 generates a .conf file. We have written a Python script to convert the .conf file to C++ (.cpp) file. Now we add the C++ file in our team's code. When we run our team, it creates triangles based on the C++ code added to the team with the help of Delaunay

triangulation. When the ball is moving in the soccer field, all players select the triangle in which the ball is. This triangle has three nodes which we included in fedit2. For any of these three points, we added a respective player point.

Fig. 4. You can see an example in this figure. Orange dot is ball. Red dots are points defined for ball and blue dots are points defined for player relative to the ball points. Pay attention that the $P_1 P_2 P_3$ triangle contains the ball so our player should be somewhere inside the $P'_1 P'_2 P'_3$ triangle.

Each of the points including the ball have a coordinate shown by X and Y. To make it simpler, ball's coordinate is shown by B.

Here is how we calculate the exact coordinate for our player based on ball's position:

$$W_b = \text{Max}(\text{dist}(P_1, B), \text{dist}(P_2, B), \text{dist}(P_3, B)) + 5$$

$$W_1 = (W_b - \text{dist}(B, P_1))^{1.2}$$

$$W_2 = (W_b - \text{dist}(B, P_2))^{1.2}$$

$$W_3 = (W_b - \text{dist}(B, P_3))^{1.2}$$

$$X = \sum_{i=1}^{i=3} W_i X_{p'_i} \div \sum_{i=1}^{i=3} W_i$$

$$Y = \sum_{i=1}^{i=3} W_i Y_{p'_i} \div \sum_{i=1}^{i=3} W_i$$

So, the final coordinate of the player is (X, Y)

This type of formation has helped us a lot at improving our team's performance and made it simpler for us to develop multiple formations for testing. Using Delaunay triangulation, we are able to use multiple formation against a team.

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